

Comparison of Frameworks for the Assessment of Decarbonisation of European National Building Stocks

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7. ANNEXES

Content:

- TABLE A1. COMPARISON OF THE ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORKS IN TERMS OF INDICATORS
- TABLE A2. INDICATORS BETWEEN THE INDICATORS OF THE NATIONAL LTRSS AND THOSE OF THE 2023 AMENDED VERSION OF THE EPBD RECAST

(b) (...) approaches to reno. (...)	Cost-effectiveness of main renovation measures (...) per building type		MD			
	Cost-effectiveness of main renovation measures (...) per climatic zone		MD			
(c) policies and actions (...)	Total energy saving potential per building sector		MD			
	Total and annual % of (...) deep and NZEB renovation		R			
	Public incentives for deep renovation		MD			
	Public and private investments in deep renovations		R			
(d) (...) policies and actions to target the worst-performing segments (...)	Energy savings from deep renovations		R			
	Public investments in policy addressing the issues mentioned (...)		MD			
	% of rented houses with EPCs below a certain performance level		R			
	Energy pov.: % of people affected by energy poverty		MD			
	Energy pov.: % of disposable household income spent on energy		MD			
	Energy pov.: arrears on utility bills		R			
	Energy pov.: population living in inadequate (...) conditions (...)		MD			
(e) (...) public buildings	% of buildings in lowest energy classes		R			
	m2 of renovated public buildings per building type		R			
	m2 of renovated public buildings per building size		R			
(f) overview of national initiatives to promote smart technologies (...)	m2 of renovated public buildings per climatic zone		R			
	N° of buildings equipped with BEMSs per building type		R			
	Public and private investments in smart technologies		R			
	Citizens participating in energy communities		MD			
	N° of graduated students (...) on energy efficiency (...)		R			
	N° of graduated students professional/technical training (...)		MD			
	N° of installers skilled in new technologies and working practices		R			
	Budget of national research programmes (...)		R			
	Participation of national universities in international scientific research projects (...)		R			
	(g) evidence-based estimate of expected energy savings and wider benefits (...)	Reduction in energy costs per household (average)		MD		
Decrease in energy poverty			R			
Actual energy savings achieved			R			
Average/aggregate indoor air quality indices (IAQIs)			R			
Thermal comfort index (TCI)			R			
Cost of avoided illnesses			R			
Reduction in health costs attributable to energy efficiency measures			R			
Reduction of whole life carbon			MD			
DALY/QALY improvements (...)			R			
Labour productivity gains from better working environment (...)			R			
Reduction of emissions			MD			
N° of jobs created per EUR million invested in the sector			MD			
GDP increase in the building sector			MD			
% energy imports for the Member State			R			
Removal/prevention of accessibility barriers (...)			MD			
(a)	N° of integrated/aggregated projects		R			
(b)	Perceived risk of energy efficiency operation		R			
(c)	Public investments as percentage (...) in energy saving		R			
	Public-private partnership initiatives		R			
(d)	Investment in energy efficiency renovation on the public building stock		R			
(e)	One-stop shop initiatives in place		MD			
	Awareness-raising initiatives (...)		MD			
(b) Roadmap for 2030, 2040, 2050	Targets for annual renovation rates (TARR): number and total floor area: per building type		M		Targets for annual renovation rates (TARR): number and total floor area: per building type	E
	TARR: number and total floor area: worst-performing		A		TARR: number and total floor area: worst-performing	E
					TARR: number and total floor area: deep renovations	A
	Targets for expected share of renovated buildings: per building type		M		Targets for expected share of renovated buildings: per building type	E
	Targets for expected share of renovated buildings: per renovation depth		A		Targets for expected share of renovated buildings: per renovation depth	E
					Targets for expected share of renovated buildings: per measures (...)	A
	Target for expected primary and final annual energy consumption: per building type		A		Target for expected primary and final annual energy consumption: per building type	E
	Target for expected primary and final annual energy consumption: per end use		A		Target for expected primary and final annual energy consumption: per end use	E
	Expected energy savings: per building type		M		Expected energy savings: per building type	E
	Share of energy from renewable sources in the building sector		A		Share of energy from renewable sources in the building sector	E
					Numerical targets for the deployment of solar energy and heat pumps in buildings	A
					Targets for the replacement of old and inefficient heaters	A
					Targets for phasing out fossil fuels from heating and cooling systems per building type	A
					Targets for phasing out fossil fuels from heating and cooling systems as a proportion of total renovation	A
					Targets for phasing out fossil fuels from heating and cooling systems for building achieving over EPC D rating	A
					Milestones and trajectories for buildings to achieve the performance classes pursuant to Article 9(1) and higher energy performance classes in line with the climate neutrality goal	A
					Targets for increase of share of renewable energy in line with the target for the share of energy from renewable sources in the building sector set out in Directive (EU)	A
					Targets for the decarbonisation of heating and cooling, including through district heating and cooling networks using renewable energy and waste heat in line with the requirements set in Articles 23 and 24 of Directive (EU)	A
					Targets for expected operational greenhouse gas emissions: per building type	M
	Targets for expected greenhouse gas emissions: per building type		A		Targets for expected whole life-cycle GHG emission (...)	A
					Targets for expected whole life-cycle GHG emission reduction (...)	M
	Targets for expected greenhouse gas emission reduction: per building type		M		Targets aligned to Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 for circular use (...)	A
					Targets to increase carbon removals (...) on buildings	A
	Expected wider benefits: Creation of new jobs		M		Expected wider benefits: Creation of new jobs	E
	Expected (...) benefits : % reduction of people affected by energy poverty		A		(...) benefits : % reduction of people affected by energy poverty	E
					(...) benefits : % reduction of people living in inadequate (...)	A
					(...) benefits : resource efficiency, (...) efficiency of water usage	A
	Increase of GDP (share and billion Euros)		M		Increase of GDP (share and billion Euros)	M
Contribution to (...) national target for GHG emissions (...)		A		Contribution to (...) national target for GHG emissions (...)	M	
Contribution to the Union's energy efficiency targets in accordance (...) [recast EED] (...) energy eff.		A		Contribution to the Union's energy efficiency targets in accordance (...) [recast EED] (...) energy eff.	E	
Contribution to the Union's energy efficiency targets in accordance [recast EED] (...) energy savings obligation		A			R	
Contribution to the Union's energy efficiency targets (...) [amended RED] (...) renewable resources (...)		A		Contribution to the Union's energy efficiency targets (...) [amended RED] (...) renewable resources (...)	E	
Contribution to the Union's energy efficiency targets (...) [amended RED] (...) renewable resources (...) building sector		A		Contribution to the Union's energy efficiency targets (...) [amended RED] (...) renewable resources (...) building sector	M	
Contribution to Union's 2030 climate target and 2050 climate neutrality goal in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2021/1119 (...)		A		Contribution to Union's 2030 climate target and 2050 climate neutrality goal in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2021/1119 (...)	E	

		(c) Overview of implemented and planned policies and measures	Policies and measures with regard to (...): (a) the identification of cost-effective approaches to renovation (...)	M	(c) Overview of implemented and planned policies and measures	Policies and measures with regard to (...): (a) the identification of cost-optimal approaches to renovation (...)	M
			(b) national minimum energy performance standards (...) to target the worst-performing segments of the national building stock	M		(b) national minimum energy performance standards (...) to target the worst-performing segments of the national building stock	E
			(c) the promotion of deep renovation of buildings (...)	M		(c) the promotion of deep renovation of buildings (...)	E
			(d) empowering and protecting vulnerable customers (...)	A		(ca) high indoor environmental quality in new and renovated buildings	A
			(e) the creation of one-stop-shops or similar mechanisms (...)	M		(d) empowering and protecting vulnerable customers (...)	E
			(f) the decarbonisation of heating and cooling (...)	A		(e) the creation of one-stop-shops or similar mechanisms (...)	E
			(g) the promotion of renewable energy sources in buildings (...)	A		(f) the decarbonisation of heating and cooling (...)	M
						(g) the promotion of renewable energy sources in buildings (...)	E
			(h) the reduction of whole life-cycle GHG emissions for the construction, renovation, operation and end of life (...)	A		(ga) the deployment of solar energy installations on buildings	A
						(h) the reduction of whole life-cycle GHG emissions for the construction, renovation, operation and end of life (...)	E
			(i) (...) treatment of construction and demolition waste (...)	A		(ha) the reduction of the overall environmental footprint (...)	A
						(i) (...) treatment of construction and demolition waste (...)	M
			(j) (...) role of renewable energy communities and (...)	A		(ia) increase in the coverage of the building stock with EPCs (...)	A
			(k) the improvement of buildings owned by public bodies (...)	M		(j) (...) role of renewable energy communities and (...)	E
			(l) the promotion of smart technologies (...) in buildings	M		(k) the improvement of buildings owned by public bodies (...)	E
			(m) addressing market barriers and market failures	A		(l) the promotion of smart technologies (...) in buildings	E
			(n) (...) promoting education, training, (...) in construction (...)	M		(m) addressing market barriers and market failures	E
						(n) promotion of skills and education, in the construction (...)	M
			(o) awareness raising campaigns and other advisory tools	A		(na) KPIs for upskilling and/or reskilling actions (...)	A
						(o) awareness raising campaigns and other advisory tools	E
						(oa) new the promotion of smart technologies for monitoring (...)	A
						(ob) new inspection schemes (...) to verify compliance with Building Automation and Control capabilities	A
						(oc) the promotion of energy management solutions (...)	A
						(od) (...) increase the coverage of (...) EPCs or alternative (...)	A
						(oe) (...) support of citizen-led energy (...) initiatives (...)	A
						Policies and measures with regard to the following elements: (a) the increase of climate resilience of buildings	E
						(b) the promotion of the energy services market	E
						(c) the increase of fire safety	E
						(d) the increase of resilience against disaster risks (...)	E
						(e) the removal of hazardous substances including asbestos;	E
						(f) accessibility for persons with disabilities	E
						Total investment needs for 2030, 2040, 2050 (million EUR)	E
						Public investments	E
		Private investments	M				
		Secured budget	E				
		Secured budget	M				
		Targets for reducing energy poverty rates	A				
		Number of households in energy poverty	A				
		List implemented and planned policies to reduce energy poverty	A				
		List of (...) funding measures to reduce energy poverty	A				

Mandatory indicators
Optional indicators

E=existing
A=added

M=modified; MD=change in domain
R=removed

